

RADIATION EFFECTS ON SiC/Al COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

SiC fiber reinforced Al composite materials are thought to be potential candidate materials for nuclear applications. Especially, continuous and multifilament-yarn SiC fibers obtained from a spun polycarbosilane precursor (PCS-SiC; Nicalon) have been intensively investigated and have been successfully produced into SiC/Al preform wire. This paper provides a part of R & D work for PCS-SiC/Al composites. Radiation effects on SiC/Al have been investigated using neutrons and electrons and have been evaluated through microstructural evolutions and mechanical property changes. Both Young's modulus and tensile strength were increased by fast neutron irradiation at 723 K, but 423 K neutron irradiation caused embrittlement in Al matrix and resulted in no indicative increase of fracture strength. X-ray analysis suggests the formation of very fine crystals of SiC in the fibers by cascade damage. In-situ observation of electron damage process under High Voltage Electron Microscope (HVEM) suggests that the suppression effect of SiC crystal formation at SiC/Al interface with simultaneous exposures to 760 K and to electron damage would be an important mechanism in the excellent resistivity to radiation damage.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic fiber reinforced metal composites (CFRMs), such as SiC/Al and C/Al, are thought to be potential candidate materials for nuclear reactors because of their unique properties of interest, especially of their low radiation induced radio-activity characteristics[1,2]. But there have been quite a few published works as to radiation effects on CFRMs[3,4].

SiC/Al composites have been intensively studied in Japan as the important part of the National R & D project on advanced composite materials[5]. One of the emphasis of this project is to develop high quality and low cost SiC/Al composite utilizing the continuous and multifilament-yarn SiC fibers obtained from a spun polycarbosilane precursor (PCS-SiC; Nicalon)[6]. SiC/Al preform wire has been successfully produced in a test plant continuously without any kind of prior surface

treatment to SiC fibers[7].

The objective of this investigation is to clarify radiation damage processes and mechanism of mechanical property changes by neutron. The final goal of this work is to develop SiC/Al composite for application to nuclear reactors.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

SiC/Al preform wires including 500 PCS-type SiC fibers were produced at Nippon Carbon Co. Ltd, by the liquid metal infiltration method. Pure aluminum, AA1050, was selected as matrix[7]. Preform wires with the fiber volume fraction about 40 % were tensile tested and three point bending tested. Also, aluminum matrix was chemically removed and SiC fibers were extracted. Then they were tensile tested by monofilament tensile test. The surface morphologies were inspected by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Microstructures of the composite were precisely inspected by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with JEM-200CX and JEM-2000FX.

Neutron irradiations were carried out using neutrons from Japan Material Test Reactor (JMTR) at 423 K to 7×10^{23} n/m² for preform wires and to 2×10^{23} n/m² at 423 K for hot pressed sheet, and neutrons from JOYO at 723 K to 1×10^{24} n/m² and 1×10^{25} n/m² for preform wires. Post irradiation experiments were performed at Reserch Institute of Iron, Steel and Other Metals, Tohoku University. The length of neutron irradiated preform wires was 12.3 mm. Post irradiation mechanical tests of preform wires were carried out by three point bending test, only.

Isochronal heat treatments were done at 823, 873 and 923 K for 64 minutes in air to clarify the effect of heat treatment and the effect of aging during neutron irradiation. Microstructure change at elevated temperatures was in-situ observed under HVEM. Condition used in HVEM experiment was,

Electron energy: 1 MeV
 Max. dose: 11 dpa (in Al)
 Test Temp.: 300, 370, 475, 760 K

RESULTS

Effects of Heat Treatments

The PCS-type SiC/Al composite material is generally subjected to elevated temperature exposure in service and also during forming processes for final products. Therefore, fundamental understandings of thermal exposures, i.e. effects of heat treatments or aging effect, are definitely required. Here, we had isochronally heat treated (at 823, 873 and 923 K for 64 minutes) preform wires. Figure 1 shows the results of the tensile tests. Both of the tensile strengths of SiC mono-filaments and preform wires decrease with increasing heat treatment temperature. The line named "Rule of mixture" is indicating the calculated values by a simple rule of mixture.

SEM fractographs of SiC/Al preform wires with different heat treatment are shown in Fig.2. As produced preform wires (Fig.2 (a)) and preform wires with 823 K heat treatment have no significant differences in fracture mode of rugged surface with little pull-out and with no detectable interfacial phase formation. In the case of 873 K heat treatment,

Fig.1 :Effect of heat treatment on tensile strength of SiC/Al preform wire and SiC extracted from the preform wire.

Fig.2 (b), many flat regions in rugged surface without pull-outs cameout, indicating the degradation of crack arrest property at matrix or interface. The 923 K heat treatment promoted the effect, as shown in Fig. 2 (c), i.e. the ratio of the flat region was larger than that at 823 K.

a; 823 K x 64 min. b; 873 K x 64 min. c; 923 K x 64 min.

Fig.2 :Effect of heat treatment on surface morphology of tensile fractured SiC/Al preform wire.

Effects of Neutron Irradiation

723 K Irradiation in JOYO

In order to study the effects of fast neutron irradiation, preform wires were irradiated in fast breeder reactor "JOYO" at 723 K, which is the typical service temperature for the utilization to fusion reactor.

Average tensile strength and Young's modulus of extracted fibers are shown in Fig. 3 (a). Young's modulus is strongly neutron fluence dependent above $1 \times 10^{24} \text{ n/m}^2$, but tensile strength shows radiation induced hardening only at $1 \times 10^{25} \text{ n/m}^2$. Three point bending test results of preform wires, Fig. 3 (b), shows similar fluence dependence as of fibers. These dependences indicate that Young's modulus is rather microstructure sensitive than tensile strength. Fracture surface after post irradiation three point bending test showed little changes in fractography by neutron irradiation, but occasionally included grainboundary dimples near interface or small cavities, suggesting that 720 K irradiation produces no significant changes in microstructures of matrix and interface.

Fig.3 :Fluence dependence of strength and Young's modulus of extracted SiC fiber; (a), and that of preform wire; (b), materials tested were neutron irradiated in JOYO.

423 K Irradiation in JMTR

Many Tokamak type fusion reactor conceptual design suggests cyclic operation of reactors. Thus the reactor materials are subjected to thermal cycles. In case of aluminum, around 420 K is known to be the peak swelling temperature range where mechanical property degradation might take place, too[8]. 423 K neutron irradiation in JMTR has been planned to evaluate radiation effects especially in aluminum matrix and interface. Figure 4 shows tensile strength increase for extracted SiC fiber as the function of fiber diameter. Mixed spectrum neutrons with the fluence of $7 \times 10^{23} \text{ n/m}^2$

Fig.4 :Effect of neutron irradiation on tensile strength of SiC fibers as the dependence on fiber size.

Fig.5 :Effect of neutron irradiation on flexural strength of hot-pressed SiC/Al sheet as the dependence of fiber volume fraction.

produced tensile strength increase almost twice as that of unirradiated SiC fibers. But for the case of SiC/Al preform wires and for the case of hot-pressed SiC/Al sheets, no clear indication of radiation induced hardening has been observed with the same neutron fluence. Neutron radiation effect on flexural strength as fiber volume fraction dependence is shown in Fig. 5. Even with the wide data scattering, flexural strength has a tendency to increase with increasing volume fraction of SiC fibers. But the strength change by neutron irradiation lies within the data scatter band and any kind of obvious radiation hardening has not been observed. Figure 6 is the fracture surfaces showing the difference in matrix ductility with and without neutron irradiation at 423 K. In the irradiated preform wires, grainboundary brittle fracture can be seen, but no detectable difference in fiber surface morphology is indicated.

A ; Irradiated

B ; Unirradiated

Fig.6 :Comparison of fracture surface in SiC/Al preform wire with and without irradiation in JMTR.

IN-SITU Observation under HVEM

In-situ observations of microstructure have been carried out under HVEMs (JEM-1250, HU-1300) from room temperature to 760 K. As for electron damage study, we used 3 µm diameter electron beam and as for image

Fig.7 :Difference of microstructure in SiC/Al under HVEM with (inside of dotted circle) and without (outside of the circle) 1 MeV electron bombardment for 93 min. at 760 K.

recording, we used largely defocused beam, i.e. weak and uniform beam. Figure 7 indicates an example of damaged microstructure at 760 K for 93 min. (11 dpa in Al). In aluminum grains, well developed dislocation structures are shown, but in SiC, no detectable change can be seen. The most significant difference in the area with thermal effect only and that with thermal and electron damage is the formation of SiC crystal at SiC/Al interface from SiC side to Al, mainly along Al cell boundary. That is, significant SiC crystal formation takes place with thermal exposure at 760 K for 93 min., but simultaneous electron damage suppresses such SiC crystal formation at interface. The suppression effect of SiC crystal formation has been also observed by lower temperature electron irradiations prior to the thermal exposure at 760 K for 93 min[9]. Another characteristic feature of damage microstructure for SiC/Al is the suppression of void formation in Al matrix between 300 and 475 K, where void formation has been reported with the same HVEM and with the same experimental condition for annealed pure Al and Al-Li alloys[10]. Figure 8 shows the microstructure development by electron bombardment at 373 K and 673 K. At 373 K, well developed dislocation structure in aluminum matrix has been observed but no void can be seen, whereas at 673 K, dislocation structure is at dynamic steady state condition including small interstitial type dislocation loops produced by electron damage. In every cases, significant microstructure change has not been observed in SiC and at the fiber-matrix interface .

DISCUSSION

Effects of Irradiation Temperature and Energy Spectrum

The results obtained from JOYO and JMTR include differences in both irradiation temperature and energy spectrum of neutrons and they are too few informations to get clear understandings of temperature and spectrum effects. But, we will try to figure out them in the followings.

As to SiC/Al, Young's modulus has a tendency to increase with increasing neutron fluence. But, the flexural strength has different

Fig.8 :Microstructural evolution in SiC/Al under HVEM with 1 MeV electron bombardment. (a)unirradiated, (b)373 K irradiated, (c)673 K irradiated

fluence dependences for JOYO and JMTR irradiation, i.e. the former increases and the latter stays with increasing total fluence. The neutron fluence dependences of tensile strength and Young's modulus for extracted SiC fiber have the same trends as reported for Nicalon fiber by K.Okamura et al.[11,12] and R.J.Price et al.[13]. The calculated rule of mixture value using the strength of extracted fiber and that of aluminum matrix coincides well with the experimental value for the case of JOYO irradiation. This is suggesting that there is little degradation of interfacial strength by neutron irradiation. In-situ observation of microstructural evolution under HVEM at 760 K suggests that there is no indication of radiation embrittlement in Al, which is also supported by SEM observation of fracture surface. In-situ experiment under HVEM also suggests that electron bombardment suppresses interfacial SiC crystal formation from fiber to matrix, which could act as degrading nuclei. This is also supported by the Weibull's analysis of strength. Thus, radiation hardening of SiC fiber is directly reflected to the strength of SiC/Al composite for in the case of JOYO irradiation.

But on the contrary, mixed spectrum neutron irradiation in JMTR at 423 K only showed strengthening of extracted fibers but slight increase in strength of preform wires and hot-pressed sheet. To clarify the degrading factor of preform wire strength in the JMTR irradiation, Weibull's analysis for extracted SiC fibers was performed. The results indicate that neutron irradiation produces no significant difference for JMTR and JOYO which implies that formation of initiation sites for fracture of SiC fiber does not seriously take place in JMTR and in JOYO irradiations. Therefore, these results are believed to be influenced through the neutron fluence dependence of interfacial strength and/or that of matrix. In-situ observation under HVEM indicates that radiation hardening in matrix and interface would be serious, although no void formation has been detected. This is partly supported by the grainboundary brittle fracture observed in JMTR irradiated preform wires. The specific fracture mode, shown in Fig. 9, is another implication that Al matrix is hardened and/or interfacial strength is degraded.

Neutron energy spectrum effect on radiation hardening of SiC fiber is simply derived with the fluence dependence of hardening for JOYO and JMTR. JMTR irradiation resulted in about three times higher hardening than

Fig. 9 :String shaped fracture of Al matrix observed in SiC/Al irradiated in JMTR.

JOYO irradiation. This tendency cannot easily understood through total amount of displacement damage, only. Because fast neutron from JOYO produce larger displacement damage than mixed spectrum neutron from JMTR. One of the important spectrum effects is helium production by transmutation damage in JMTR and negligible production in JOYO. But, the total neutron fluences applied are too small to be taken into account of the direct transmutation effect, i.e. helium bubble hardening. The possible mechanism is the production of very fine SiC crystal in amorphous SiC and transmuted helium would act as nucleation agent or stabilizer of embryo. Figure 10 is an example of high resolution TEM micrographs of SiC, where very fine SiC crystals are dispersed in amorphous SiC. The thickness of those fine crystals is 3 - 5 crystal layers. Therefore, if sub-cascade is produced in the crystals, which could stay as amorphous state for relatively low temperature irradiation. This assumption also consistent with the fact that neutrons from JMTR produces higher hardening than those from JOYO. This assumption is also consistent with the fact that JMTR irradiation affects X-ray diffraction results; broad SiC peak has changed into rather broader peak by irradiation in JMTR. This behavior is suggesting that fine dispersed SiC crystals in SiC fiber of as fabricated SiC/Al preform wire have changed into smaller crystals with higher number density by radiation damage.

Fig.10 :High resolution TEM image of SiC fiber in SiC/Al.

Fig.11 :Schematic illustration of the effects of thermal and neutron exposures on Young's modulus and tensile strength of SiC/Al.

Difference of Materials Response by Thermal Treatment and Radiation

As mentioned the above, there are significant difference of the dependences of tensile strength and Young's modulus on thermal treatment and on neutron irradiation. Figure 11 is a schematic illustration of those dependences. The dependences on heat treatment temperature for SiC fibers have been previously reported and they were related with the crystallization of SiC from amorphous state[6]. The increase in Young's modulus due to structural change to crystalline state agrees well with physics based model. Our present understanding is that neutron irradiation produces very fine crystalline particles in amorphous SiC which introduce hardening instead of reducing tensile strength. There are no evidence as to the formation of very fine crystals in the amorphous SiC, but sub-cascades induced by neutron damage could be heterogenous nucleation sites for SiC. That means, if we can distribute a great number of nucleation sites, the same order as those produced by neutron irradiation, the improvement of tensile strength and Young's modulus, simultaneously, will be easily achieved. The production of high modulus and high strength type SiC/Al composite materials brings great advantages especially for applications in aeronautical and space technologies.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The effect of thermal treatment was studied and degradation mechanisms based on crystallization of amorphous SiC was proposed. Also SiC crystal formation at SiC/Al interface at 760 K would be an origin of thermal degradation of mechanical properties at above 823 K.
- (2) The effects of neutron irradiation were studied using fission neutrons from JOYO and JMTR. The SiC/Al composite and SiC fiber showed excellent stability under neutron irradiations.
- (3) Increments of tensile strength and Young's modulus were observed by irradiation in FBR (JOYO). A heterogenous nucleation of SiC crystal

due to sub-cascade damage was interpreted to be the dominant mechanism. This model is supported by the results of X-ray analysis and lattice imaging in high-resolution TEM observation.

- (4) In-situ experiment under 1 MV HVEM indicates that SiC crystal formation at interface is suppressed by simultaneous exposures to 760 K and to electron damage. This would be an important mechanism as to the excellent stability of PCS-SiC/Al for neutron damage.

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